

Transforming IT Services : Strategic Approaches and Lessons Learned

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ABSTRACT

The paper reviewed relevant articles on strategic pursuit management. Being a conceptual paper, I have started by highlighting the overview / essence of strategic pursuit management and elaborating the role of Pursuit leader. This was followed by research and refereeing different proven strategies and factors that may lead to discussions on factors that affect strategy formulation, strategy implementation as well as factors bedeviling strategy implementation. Essentiality of strategic management practices as a radical improvement method was equally highlighted.

Keywords : Strategic Management; Strategy Planning; Strategy Implementation

I. INTRODUCTION

In the constantly changing world of IT solutions, professionals with exceptional abilities and unique skills often distinguish themselves from the rest of the crowd. This article will cover some exceptional strategies employed by individuals in the field to pursue and secure large pursuits successfully. There are different concepts, principles approach followed to lead a successful.

Strategic Pursuit management is a niche in the IT industry that involves managing the evolution of strategies that are important to an organization's bottom line. It is a systematic and disciplined approach of identifying, qualifying and winning a large value deal. The overall process involves developing and executing a win strategy by engaging with the customer and delivering a compelling solution and proposal. It is

As per Adam Thorp, [Strategic pursuits and the capture management process \(julianmidwinter.com.au\)](http://julianmidwinter.com.au) while the goal of strategic pursuits, capture management, and bid management is to win opportunities. They are all essential steps in this process, and they have to work together smoothly and pass on the information effectively to create a winning proposal that meets the client's needs.

These steps to winning are defined in his white paper as follows,

- Pursuit management – a segmentation exercise reveals an opportunity, or a contract requires renewal. This could entail a competitive tender or an opportunity to market your business so you can present and exhibit an unsolicited proposal
- Capture management (alternatively 'Opportunity management') – is the process of understanding,

creating and carrying out your strategy and technique to win the pursuit. The purpose of the capture process is to change from an unfamiliar position to a preferred supplier position with the buyer before the bid is published.

- Bid management – is the process of carrying out and overseeing the production of the written submission and the presentation of your case. Winning submissions need a deliberate and proven bid management process. The Pursuit and Capture teams have a vital role in transforming the insights, customer knowledge, and solutions that has been created and verified into bid-ready material before the bid is released.

In conclusion, Adam Thorp emphasizes that the seamless integration of strategic pursuits, capture management, and bid management is crucial for winning opportunities. Each step plays a vital role in the overall process, from identifying and segmenting opportunities to crafting and presenting a compelling proposal. By effectively passing on information and working collaboratively, these processes ensure that the final submission meets the client's needs and stands out as a winning proposal. This holistic approach not only enhances the chances of success but also positions the business as a preferred supplier, ready to meet and exceed client expectations.

II. Role of Pursuit professionals

Strategic management professionals are sought after by organizations because they have a profound knowledge of business, finance, corporate planning, and more. The role of an effective Strategic Pursuit leader is crucial in the world of large pursuits and multimillion-dollar pursuits. They require the strategy and abilities that help them stay ahead of the client, comprehending their specific needs, and designing solutions that match the clients' overall business goals. Pursuit Leads are responsible for building strong relationships with

clients, understanding their unique needs, and crafting solutions that align with the clients' overarching business objectives.

Pursuit leaders stand out by their ability to offer smart suggestions that enable clients to accomplish their objectives while making sure that the solutions provided are technically solid. This skill is essential for two reasons. First, it generates a chance to sell. Second, it puts the sales professional in the scene early when they can have the most impact.

The success of a Pursuit Lead often hinges on whether they can create a WIN-WIN situation for their Client and their Employers. Nearly every large pursuit involves cooperation across multiple departments. This can also be the most difficult challenge to overcome. Each department has its own way of working, while the solution you present to the client needs to have a unique wrapper that brings everything together. The pursuit leaders have a key role in this, by establishing clear common goals and objectives, ensuring coherent messaging, fostering innovation, leading interdepartmental brainstorming, and giving regular feedback and evaluation as the story develops.

Based on experience and research conducted below are some pointers for overall responsibilities of a Pursuit leader,

- Forming and leading a group of skilled salespeople and experts who can work well together and provide value to the customer.
- Planning and carrying out a pursuit strategy that fits the client's needs, goals, and decision criteria, and differentiates the solution from the competitors.
- Creating and keeping a relationship with the key decision makers and influencers in the client organization, and influencing their perception of the solution and the provider.
- Controlling the pursuit process and ensuring that the team follows the best practices and guidelines for qualification, proposal development, presentation, negotiation, and closing.

- Handling the pursuit budget and resources, and ensuring that the team meets the deadlines and quality standards.
- Organizing and leading a team of skilled salespeople and experts who can work together effectively and deliver value to the client.
- Crafting and executing a pursuit tactic that aligns with the client's needs, goals, and decision criteria, and distinguishes the solution from the rivals.
- Establishing and preserving a bond with the key decision makers and influencers in the client organization, and influencing their impression of the solution and the provider.
- Steering the pursuit process and ensuring that the team follows the best practices and guidelines for qualification, proposal development, presentation, negotiation, and closing.
- Overseeing the pursuit budget and resources, and ensuring that the team meets the deadlines and quality standards.

According to an article by Richardson Sales and training, below are 4 Sales Pursuit Strategy which I agree on and can relate to IT services Strategic deals I have led in the past.

1. **Establish a partnership-oriented tone:** Transactions are temporary, but partnerships are long-lasting. To build a strong relationship, sales professionals should focus on mutually beneficial outcomes. This sense of shared goals must be conveyed through the sales professional's words and actions from the strategic prospecting stage through the negotiation.
2. **Drive momentum and consensus:** Sales professionals must take the lead in creating a sense of urgency. Competing priorities can distract customers and cause them to lose focus. Risk-averse behavior compounds as more stakeholders, each with their own concerns, enter the picture. Therefore, sales professionals must align and

3. **Continually Qualify:** To ensure that the deal stays on track, sales professionals must continuously evaluate the customer's needs throughout the buying process. As the customer's needs change, the scope of the sale may also change. Stakeholders may enter and exit, and this shifting sphere of influence can cause the deal to drift or die. Effective sales professionals identify red flags and reevaluate the deal to determine if it's still viable. They need the insight and resolve to let opportunities go when necessary.
4. **Consider the Emotions in Play:** Sales professionals must be aware of the emotions that drive customer behavior. Although customers may appear analytical, emotions can wield equal, if not greater, influence. With money at stake, customers may feel obligated to present each decision as one driven by logic and research. Sales professionals must watch for emotions like fear, which can prevent the sale. They must motivate action that combats the status quo without appearing pushy.

III. PROVEN STRATEGIES

Over the years, with multiple success and failures I have come to follow a unique approach, which I like to call **The E3 Principle**. This helps me stay focused on the needs of my pursuit and keep it unique:

- **Exclusive Solutions with Innovative Offerings:**

When it comes to serving clients, one size rarely fits all. Every business has unique challenges, goals, and requirements. Therefore, crafting exclusive solutions that meet clients' specific needs is essential. This means taking the time to thoroughly understand a client's needs, objectives, and constraints. Validating the same using available data and driving deep data analysis – providing insights to clients they may have ignored. By doing so, you can create solutions that are specifically designed to address their challenges and help them achieve their goals. Tailoring solutions in this way not only increases the likelihood of success but also demonstrates a genuine commitment to meeting your client's needs.

While an Exclusive Solution forms the core, Innovation is a driving force in today's rapidly evolving business landscape. Where possible introducing new ideas, approaches, and technologies to better serve your clients. Innovation can take many forms, from adopting cutting-edge technologies to rethinking traditional processes. It allows you to provide clients with solutions that are not only effective but also forward-thinking and capable of adapting to changing circumstances. Innovative offerings also demonstrate your commitment to staying current and continuously improving to better serve your clients.

In summary, I would emphasize the importance of creating Exclusive Solutions clubbed with Innovative offerings. This approach allows you to demonstrate a deep commitment to your clients' success while staying at the forefront of your industry. It's a recipe for building strong client relationships and a competitive edge in the market and demonstrates a commitment to adding genuine value.

- **Expressive Storytelling:**

Your story is only as good as it is told, the narration plays a larger role than you can imagine in ensuring that the client sees the uniqueness of your solution, the

effort involved and the benefits it brings to them. Effective communication is critical. Providing concise, relevant information that addresses key client questions—Why, What, How, Where, When, and Who, this approach ensures that you cover all aspects of the information that your clients might be interested in

When you use expressive storytelling to communicate, you're not just transmitting data; you're building a bridge of trust. Clients are more likely to trust a message that is well-structured, honest, and delivered with empathy. Moreover, this approach enhances clarity, ensuring that your clients have a crystal-clear understanding of the information you're conveying. It's about anticipating their needs and providing comprehensive answers to these questions.

In summary, expressive storytelling is a powerful tool for effective communication. It involves packaging information in an engaging manner, while also being concise and relevant. By addressing key client questions and building trust through clear, well-structured communication, you not only meet your clients' information needs but also build stronger, more productive relationships.

- **Elastic Financial Models:**

Elastic financial models refer to financial frameworks and strategies that possess flexibility and adaptability. These models are designed to respond to changes, uncertainties, and evolving circumstances in a changing IT Landscape.

Flexibility and adaptability in financial models are key. The tech world is dynamic, and a one-size-fits-all approach often falls short of meeting the diverse needs and goals of clients. A flexible financial model can be adjusted or fine-tuned to accommodate technological innovation, investments in new trends, and achieving financial goals. It can adapt to shifts in the economic environment, changes in regulations, or unforeseen events such as market volatility.

Some key characteristics of elastic financial models may include predictive cash flows, flexible rolling forecasts, dynamic budgeting based on volumes, as well as gain share models that link payouts to growth and achievement milestones. These features empower organizations to adapt swiftly to changing financial landscapes and foster growth while mitigating risks.

In summary, elastic financial models on large pursuits should be designed to be flexible, adaptable, and responsive to changing financial needs and an ever so changing IT Technology Landscape. These models help clients maintain financial security and achieve their long-term goals.

While the E3 principle emphasizes an approach for successfully managing a large pursuit. Let's delve into some factors that can inadvertently relegate your pursuit to the bottom of the pile.

- **Not Listening to client needs:** It's a common pitfall to lose sight of the client's specific needs and instead construct your proposal based solely on your organization's strengths and capabilities. To excel in pursuit management, it's crucial to have a deep understanding of what truly appeals to your client and what factors drive their decision-making. Listening attentively and aligning your solution with the client's unique requirements is pivotal.
- **Underestimating Competitors:** Neglecting to thoroughly comprehend your competition, their existing relationships, and their strengths can leave you vulnerable to unexpected challenges. In the realm of pursuit management, this oversight can be devastating. Staying informed about your competitors, anticipating their moves, and continuously innovating your approach is essential to keeping your pursuit at the forefront.
- **Not Monitoring External Factors:** Successful pursuit management involves more than just looking inward; it requires a keen awareness of external factors. This includes staying informed

about changes in client leadership, being attuned to market dynamics that may impact your client's business and understanding what's making your client's industry news. These external factors can significantly influence the success of your pursuit.

The E3 principles provide a framework for effective pursuit management, but certain missteps can undermine your efforts. To excel in this endeavor, it's imperative to pay close attention to the client's needs, respect and understand your competition, and keep a watchful eye on external factors that could impact your pursuit's success.

Another interesting article I found on Medium by Priyadarshi Tripathy, who has depicted and explained Pursuit management with 5C model he developed. Per him, Creativity, Collaboration, Communication, Content, Context, and Commercial are the five critical factors (5C) to ensure the success of a pursuit.

Priyadarshi Tripathy's model of 5Cs for successful pursuit management with *Speed, Quality and assured Win*. [My 5C Model: Mastering the Art of Pursuit Management | by Priyadarshi Tripathy | HUMAN | DAD | BELIEVER | SoloArtist. Writings & Creatives. | Medium](#)

This model depicts how the 5Cs are the foundational elements for any pursuit to be run and striven for success. the pursuit of a client's requirements, it is

essential to meticulously analyze the What, Why, When, Where, and How of any client request. This process is imperative for a well-defined opportunity management mechanism, especially during the opportunity qualification stage. Factors such as the current state of financial performance, budget appetite, competitive landscape, buying patterns, and relationships with key stakeholders must be thoroughly examined. This information becomes the core of the Solution construct or Context. Your proposed solution should fit the client's requirements like a lock and key pair, addressing their specific needs and differentiating it from generic offerings that might suit various industries. Collaboration is emphasized, highlighting the need for teamwork, cohesion, and convergence across diverse backgrounds and expertise. The Context must align with Commerce, considering budget constraints and focusing not only on high margins but also on the lowest possible cost. Content is stressed as a critical communication tool, with a focus on engaging proposal writers and editors to ensure clarity and impact. Lastly, Creativity is highlighted, emphasizing the importance of packaging information innovatively, engaging creative minds, information designers, and graphics artists to present a proposal that goes beyond good, showcasing a deep understanding of the customer's needs and expectations. The key to a great proposal lies in demonstrating how the company's solutions uniquely address and fulfill the customer's requirements, going beyond credentials and methods to focus on delivering tangible benefits and value.

As per [Kevin Doddrell](#), in his article on [The Five Keys to Winning the Largest Deals \(revenuestorm.com\)](#) says and I agree that throughout our sales career, we may encounter the chance to compete for a deal that is larger than any we have ever won (or lost) before. These chances usually fill us with both excitement and nervousness. We are confident that our company supports us to lead the opportunity. There is likely to be a considerable amount of money spent on

supporting the bid team. It could be the only opportunity we get to work on.

As the pursuit leader, we must realize that the win rate on large strategic deals should be compared to the best-in-class at around 70% or higher. Anything lower than this suggests that some or all of the following principles have been ignored.

1. Get Your Team Together

A team which is totally focused on winning the opportunity is critical. Leverage your internal contacts and resources and build a team that can commit for the duration of the opportunity. The reason this is critical is clients are looking more closely at the team and looking for consistency. This is demonstrated by the number of times presentations are required to be conducted by the actual delivery team, and not the selling team. A consistent and aligned pursuit team brings energy and focus to the pursuit.

2. Use Qualification to Gain an Early Advantage

The general approach to qualification is to decide as to whether to compete and commit resources to an opportunity. While this is a valuable outcome of qualification, there is a more important role of good qualification. By using a structured approach to qualification, such as a [Qualifier Tool](#), you can assess initial vulnerabilities, and you can see which early actions can enable you to gain a quick competitive advantage. Proactive actions are designed to increase early collaboration with the client. The objective being to gain commitment from them on their most valuable assets – their people. If you can engage the client early by introducing new ideas and thought leadership around their approach, then the very activity of collaboration will create a relationship advantage. An early relationship advantage will create momentum in your direction ahead of the competition.

3. Set Your Strategy Before Designing the Solution

Too many teams dive straight into the solution before considering the overarching strategy for the opportunity. Instead, establish the strategy by having a kickoff session for the deal, maybe two to three hours. Make sure everyone on the team has an equitable amount of input during this initial session, as consistency of messaging and Go-to-Market Strategy is set early in the deal. If there is a formal proposal to submit, this also anchors the consistency of messaging, Go-to-Market Strategy, and Win Theme. This kickoff also sets a critical next step – establishing the action plan to gain competitive intelligence, which will invariably be lacking.

4. Establish a Tool and Coaching Cadence

One of the slippery slopes that can swallow up a pursuit team is getting so “into” the deal they do not regularly revisit their strategy. They live “in the maze” and don’t take the time to look “down on the maze.” If possible, recruit an independent coach – someone who can take a pragmatic, independent approach to constantly test the team and open new thinking. For a deal which is say, 12 months in duration, meeting as a team and revisiting the overall strategy at least every three weeks is critical. Using sales tools is a must, as is updating them every three weeks for review in the strategy session.

5. Research and Calculated Risk

Proactivity and taking calculated risk will result in a higher win rate than reactivity and compliance, especially in an RFP situation. In general, clients are hungry for thought leadership and new thinking. It is important to try and gain a competitive advantage in the first half of the sales cycle by encouraging new thinking and constantly looking for proactive moves that can be made. These, if well executed, will often create breakthrough momentum during the deal life cycle. Proactivity does increase the element of risk in execution, which can be managed through better research. Research on business priorities, and even

more importantly, personal agendas, is fundamental to maintaining manageable risk.

The five key elements above will create the teamwork, strategic approach, and tactical execution plan to significantly increase your chances of deal winning your next largest opportunity!

To summarize, Kevin Doddrell underscores that securing large strategic deals necessitates a dedicated and unified team, early and thorough qualification, a clear strategy, consistent coaching and review, and proactive risk-taking. By following these principles, pursuit leaders can greatly improve their chances of success and effectively manage the complexities of high-stakes opportunities. This comprehensive approach ensures that teams are not only competitive but also excel in winning the most significant deals of their careers.

Another interesting article I came across while researching was [How to Develop an Effective Win Strategy \[Guide + Template\] \(ksiadvantage.com\)](#) by [Written by Ashley Kayes, CPP APMP](#)

The article “How to Develop an Effective Win Strategy” from Key Solutions outlines a structured approach to creating a successful win strategy for proposals. It emphasizes that each win strategy should be tailored to the specific procurement opportunity and involves four key steps:

1. **Initiate a Win Strategy Kickoff:** This is a planning session with the Capture and Proposal Team to set or refine the win strategy, covering strengths, weaknesses, competition, and key themes.
2. **Implement the Decision Block Process®:** This process groups related issues to be addressed in a logical sequence, helping to minimize proposal risks by resolving key issues early.
3. **Articulate the Value Proposition:** This step involves summarizing why the company should

be awarded the contract, providing evaluators with key points to support their decision.

4. **Create the Win Strategy Document:** This document serves as a roadmap for winning the contract, detailing the value proposition, major themes, and key elements of the proposal.

The article stresses the importance of flexibility in the win strategy to adapt to changes and competitive considerations throughout the opportunity lifecycle. Regular reviews and updates at key milestones ensure the strategy remains relevant and effective

IV. Barriers to winning a potential deal/ Risk/ Factors influencing the implementation of large deal

Base on my research ([The 4 Guiding Principles of a Sales Opportunity Pursuit Strategy \(richardson.com\)](#) ([How to Apply a Solid Bid Pursuit Strategy to Improve Your Win Rate \(ksiadvantage.com\)](#) and [Strategic pursuits and the capture management process \(julianmidwinter.com.au\)](#) I found these below major reasons behind failure or barriers for not wining

One of the most significant barriers is the lack of a well-defined sales opportunity pursuit strategy Sales professionals need to have a clear plan of action that keeps them ahead of every curve in the road to the sale. They need to execute the skills to be buyer-centric, strategic, and differentiated to work within the buyer's changing world. Sales professionals must pull customers through the process by helping them gain clarity, evaluate options, increase confidence in the economic value of the solution, increase confidence in the ease of acquisition, and alleviate fears.

Another barrier is the lack of a **solid bid pursuit strategy**. Applying a thorough strategy in the opportunities pursued and starting pursuits earlier to gain an understanding of the customer and competitive landscape can help improve overall win rates .

To overcome these barriers, sales professionals can adhere to a set of guiding principles that generate and maintain momentum throughout the sales pursuit. The 4 Guiding Principles of a Sales Pursuit Strategy are:

1. **Set a tone for Mutual Partnership:** Transactions end. Partnerships last. The key to building a relationship is focusing on mutually beneficial outcomes.
2. **Drive Momentum and Consensus:** Competing priorities distract customers and cause them to lose focus. Risk-averse behavior compounds as more stakeholders, each with their concerns, enter the picture. Therefore, sales professionals must take the lead and create momentum. Doing so means driving consensus. This process requires sales professionals to align and realign decision-makers.
3. **Continually Qualify:** The customer's needs change throughout the buying process. As a result, the scope of the sale also changes. Stakeholders enter and exit. This shifting sphere of influence can cause the deal to drift or die. Effective sales professionals identify red flags and reevaluate the deal to determine if it's still real. They need the insight and resolve to let opportunities go when necessary.
4. **Consider the Emotions in Play:** Customers often appear analytic. With money at stake, they feel obligated to present each decision that they make as one driven by logic and research. In truth, emotions wield equal, if not greater, influence. Sales professionals must watch for emotions like fear, which can prevent the sale. They must motivate action that combats the status quo without appearing pushy.

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